

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of *m*-Cresol by Vanadium(V) in Presence of Salicylic and Substituted Salicylic Acids in Dilute Perchloric Acid Medium

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The kinetics of the oxidation of *m*-cresol by vanadium(V) in presence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids was studied in perchloric acid medium. The reaction is first order each in V(V) and *m*-cresol. Plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[L]$ (where L represents salicylic or substituted salicylic acid) were found to be linear with positive intercepts on $1/k_1$ -axes, suggesting the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between V(V) and the ligand which is believed to be a more potent oxidant. The reaction is acid-catalysed and the plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[H^+]$ was found to be linear with a positive intercept on $1/k_1$ -axis. The applicability of Marcus theory to this reaction is discussed.

WE have recently reported the oxalic acid¹ and EDTA^{2,3}-catalysed oxidations of organic and inorganic compounds by vanadium(V). The results have shown that these carboxylic acids form complexes with vanadium(V), the complexes being more potent oxidants than free V(V). While extending the study to other ligands, we found that salicylic acid catalyses the oxidation of organic compounds by vanadium(V). Recently Pelizzetti *et al*⁴ applied Marcus theory to the oxidation of organic compounds by iron(III) complexes. Not much work, however, was reported in this field. Hence we have investigated the applicability of Marcus theory in the case of oxidations by V(V) complexes. For this we have investigated the kinetics of oxidation of *m*-cresol with V(V) in the presence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids and found that Marcus correlation is valid for this vanadium(V) oxidation.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Sodium vanadate solution was prepared and standardised according to the method of Gopala Rao *et al*⁵; *m*-cresol solution was prepared just before use and standardized bromometrically. Salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids (E. Merck, 'pro analysi') were used after recrystallization. 5-Nitro salicylic acid (m. p. 226°) was prepared by the standard method⁶ and twice recrystallized. 3,5-Dibromosalicylic acid was prepared by brominating salicylic acid with liquid bromine at 10° and it was recrystallized twice from acetic acid (m. p. 180°). The purity of the compound was checked by taking the ir spectrum. All these solutions were made in glacial acetic acid. All other materials used were of AR grade.

The experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions in 80% (v/v) acetic acid medium and at constant ionic strength (μ). The

reaction was followed by quenching aliquots of reaction mixture at different time intervals in sulphuric acid solution containing a known excess of Fe(II) solution and the unreacted Fe(II) was titrated against standard V(V) solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as indicator. The temperature was maintained constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by Remi RK 701 ultra cryostat.

Toshniwal pH meter CL 46 was used to measure the redox potentials of V(V)/V(IV) couple in the presence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids and these redox potentials were used in the Marcus plot.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction in the presence and absence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids was found to be 2 moles of V(V) to one mole of *m*-cresol. Dienone was found to be one of the products as evidenced by spot test⁷. The stoichiometric results (Table 1) and the product analysis indicate that

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY OF THE REACTION
[H⁺]=0.5M; [Salicylic acid]=3.0 × 10⁻³M;
Acetic acid=80% (v/v); Temp.=25 ± 0.1°

[V(V)] × 10 ³ M	[<i>m</i> -cresol] × 10 ³ M	[V(V)] × 10 ³ M unreacted	[V(V)] × 10 ³ M reacted	$\frac{[V(V)]}{[m\text{-cresol}]}$
2.0	0.30	1.39	0.61	2.09
4.0	0.40	3.21	0.79	1.98
6.0	0.50	4.98	1.02	2.04

there is no induced oxidation by atmospheric oxygen and further, salicylic and substituted salicylic acids are not consumed through the oxidation of these ligands by V(V).

Since *m*-cresol is known to be oxidized by V(V)⁸, kinetic runs were carried out in the absence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids. At the low temperatures and the concentrations employed in this

kinetic study, the extent of uncatalysed reaction during the time taken for following the rates of catalysed reactions has been found to be negligibly small.

Results and Discussion

The reaction is first order in $V(V)$ as revealed by the linear plots of $\log[V(V)]$ vs time under the conditions $[m\text{-cresol}] \gg [V(V)]$. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) are independent of the initial $[V(V)]$ (Table 2). The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) at different $[m\text{-cresol}]$ are presented in Table 2. It is evident from the data that the pseudo-first order rate constant k_1 is directly proportional to $[m\text{-cresol}]$, indicating the first order behaviour in $m\text{-cresol}$ also (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING $[m\text{-cresol}]$, $[V(V)]$ AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) ON THE REACTION RATE

$[V(V)] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[Salicylic\ acid] = 1.6 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 $[H^+] = 0.50 M$; Acetic acid = 80% (v/v); Temp. = $10 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$10^3 [m\text{-cresol}]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	$10^3 \times [V(V)]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	Ionic strength (μ)	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}
4.0	2.28	1.0	2.30	0.50	2.28
8.0	4.59	1.5	2.21	0.75	2.23
12.0	6.80	2.0	2.28	1.00	2.12
16.0	9.01	2.5	2.26	1.25	2.42
20.0	11.6	—	—	1.50	2.35

φ at $[m\text{-cresol}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING $[LIGAND]$ ON THE REACTION RATE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$[V(V)] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[m\text{-cresol}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 0.5$
 $[H^+] = 0.50 M$; Acetic acid = 80% (v/v)

$10^3 \times [ligand]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3, \text{min}^{-1}$ at		
	5°	10°	15°
Salicylic acid			
1.6	1.76	2.23	2.62
2.4	2.12	3.09	3.54
3.2	2.55	3.73	4.30
4.0	3.11	4.15	4.94
4.8	3.73	4.76	5.48
Sulphosalicylic acid			
1.6	1.30	1.81	2.33
2.4	1.59	2.28	3.17
3.2	1.93	3.08	3.86
4.0	2.46	3.44	4.45
4.8	2.71	3.91	4.94
5-Nitro salicylic acid			
1.6	0.89	1.38	1.84
2.4	1.20	1.95	2.51
3.2	1.41	2.33	3.07
4.0	1.63	2.81	3.55
4.8	1.79	3.03	3.96
3,5-Dibromo salicylic acid			
1.6	2.08	2.42	2.70
2.0	2.65	3.03	3.35
2.4	2.87	3.65	4.00
2.8	3.56	4.27	4.63
3.2	4.05	4.80	5.26

Effect of varying $[ligand]$: The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_1 , were determined at different $[ligand]$, keeping the concentrations of the other reactants constant. Plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[L]$ were found to be linear with positive slopes and intercepts on $1/k_1$ -axes (Table 3), suggesting the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between $V(V)$ and the ligand.

Dependence on acidity: The influence of acid on the rate of oxidation has been studied and it is found that the reaction is acid-catalysed. The plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[H^+]$ was found to be linear with a positive intercept on $1/k_1$ -axis (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING $[ACID]$ ON THE REACTION RATE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$[V(V)] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[m\text{-cresol}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 0.5 M$
 $[ligand] = 1.6 \times 10^{-2} M$; Acetic acid = 80% (v/v)

$[H^+]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3, \text{min}^{-1}$ at		
	5°	10°	15°
Salicylic acid			
0.1	0.66	0.87	0.88
0.2	1.09	1.41	1.46
0.3	1.38	1.82	1.94
0.4	1.60	2.08	2.32
0.5	1.76	2.27	2.62
Sulphosalicylic acid			
0.1	0.48	0.56	0.74
0.2	0.79	0.81	1.30
0.3	1.01	1.11	1.72
0.4	1.17	1.35	2.06
0.5	1.30	1.61	2.33
5-Nitro salicylic acid			
0.1	0.34	0.50	0.58
0.2	0.55	0.84	1.01
0.3	0.70	1.09	1.35
0.4	0.81	1.31	1.62
0.5	0.89	1.38	1.84
3,5-Dibromo salicylic acid			
0.1	0.70	0.73	0.75
0.2	1.21	1.31	1.36
0.3	1.60	1.77	1.88
0.4	1.90	2.15	2.32
0.5	2.08	2.42	2.70

Effect of ionic strength (μ): Addition of sodium perchlorate does not produce any appreciable change in the rate of the reaction (Table 2).

Rossotti and Rossotti⁶ have shown that $V(V)$ at $pH < 1$ mostly exists in the form of VO_2^+ . With increasing $[H^+]$ this species is believed to be transformed into $V(OH)_2^{2+}$. Panduranga Rao and coworkers reported evidence for the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between $V(V)$ and salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids^{11,12}. In the light of these considerations, we propose that a 1 : 1 complex of $V(V)$ and salicylic or substituted salicylic acids is formed prior to the rate-determining step, the complex being a more potent oxidant than uncomplexed $V(V)$. The extra reactivity of this complex is presumably due to the presence of electrophilic carboxylic groups in the complex. The following scheme of mechanism accounts for all the observed kinetic results.

This leads to the rate law,

$$-\frac{d[\text{V}(\text{V})]}{dt} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{V}(\text{V})][\text{L}][\text{H}^+][\text{Substrate}]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+][\text{L}]}$$

Under the conditions $[\text{Sub}] \gg [\text{V}(\text{V})]$, the pseudo-first order rate constant k_1 , is given by

$$k_1 = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{L}][\text{H}^+][\text{Substrate}]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+][\text{L}]}$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{1}{k K_1 K_2 [\text{L}][\text{H}^+][\text{Sub}]} + \frac{1}{k K_2 [\text{L}][\text{Sub}]} + \frac{1}{k [\text{Sub}]}$$

Thus the plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{L}]$ and $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ should be straight lines with positive slopes and intercepts. This has actually been observed providing kinetic evidence for the complex formation between vanadium(V) and salicylic or substituted salicylic acids. This type of acid dependence in V(V) oxidations has been reported earlier by us¹ and by Sengupta *et al*^{1a}.

From the slopes and intercepts of the plots mentioned above, the values of k , K_1 , K_2 were calculated and are presented in Tables 5 and 6. From the rate data, the activation parameters have been determined and these results are listed in Table 5.

TABLE 5—THE VALUES OF SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS (k) AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Ligand	k lit. mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ at			$E_a^\ddagger$ K.cal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal deg ⁻¹
	5°	10°	15°		
Salicylic acid	2.08	2.56	3.02	6.40	35.8
Sulpho salicylic acid	1.85	2.37	2.81	7.71	31.4
5-Nitro salicylic acid	1.00	1.66	2.34	15.91	3.1
3,5-Dibromo salicylic acid	10.00	16.66	25.70	1.59	50.0

According to Marcus¹⁴ the free energy of activation $\Delta G^\ddagger$ for an outer-sphere electron-transfer

reaction is related to the overall free energy change, ΔG , of the reaction by the relation

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \lambda/4 (1 + \Delta G/\lambda)^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

where λ is a parameter related to the reorganization of the inner and outer coordination spheres of the reacting complex. If the reorganization term λ is $\gg \Delta G$, the quadratic term drops out and the equation (1) simplifies¹⁵ to

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \lambda/4 + 0.5 \Delta G \quad \dots (2)$$

Since the overall free energy change ΔG is proportional to the difference in the redox potentials of oxidizing and reducing couples, (E_2 and E_1 respectively) and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ is proportional to $\log k$, equation (2) changes to¹⁶

$$\log k = 8.5(E_2 - E_1) + \text{constant} \quad \dots (3)$$

For a series of substituted ligands and for the same reductant (λ and E_1 are constant) the equation assumes the form

$$\log k = 8.5 E_2 + \text{constant} \quad \dots (4)$$

where E_2 is the redox potential of the oxidizing couple. Subsequently, Marcus has reported that this correlation is also valid for redox reactions proceeding via inner-sphere mechanisms¹⁷. Thus, for closely related ligands, $\log$ (rate constant) must be linearly related to redox potential E_2 of the oxidizing couple with theoretical slope equal to 8.5.

To test the validity of this correlation, we determined the rate constant k (as defined in the mechanism) and also the redox potential of the oxidizing couple, V(V)/V(IV), in the presence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids which form complexes with vanadium(V) and found that $\log k$ is linearly related to the redox potential of V(V)/V(IV) couple with a slope equal to 9 which is in fair agreement with the theoretical slope of 8.5. (Fig. 1). This shows the applicability of Marcus theory for the present reaction.

Recently, Pelizzetti *et al* have verified this correlation in organic oxidations by metal complexes^{4,18}. This correlation has also been tested in a number of electron-transfer reactions between metal complexes proceeding via both inner^{19,20} and outer-sphere²¹ mechanisms.

TABLE 6—THE VALUES OF K_1 , K_2 AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Ligand	K_1, M^{-1}			(ΔH) K.cal/mole	K_2, M^{-1}			(ΔH) K.cal/mole
	5°	10°	15°		5°	10°	15°	
Salicylic acid	1.82	1.32	0.97		35.2	44.9	53.0	8.22
Sulpho salicylic acid	1.80	1.27	0.99	-12.54	27.9	36.3	50.1	11.97
5-Nitro salicylic acid	1.81	1.41	1.02		37.5	42.9	46.7	5.70
3,5-Dibromo salicylic acid	1.84	1.88	0.95		7.2	6.0	5.2	7.14

Fig. 1. Relationship between the logarithms of the specific rate constant for the oxidation of *m*-cresol by different V(V)-ligand complexes (10° , $\mu=0.50M$) and the formal redox potential of V(V)/V(IV) couple in the presence of salicylic and substituted salicylic acids
 (1) 5-Nitrosalicylic acid
 (2) Sulphosalicylic acid
 (3) Salicylic acid
 (4) 3,5-Dibromosalicylic acid.

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